

TO RESIDUE

Tactics for Not-Building
and
Activating Wanderspace

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RE-ST
UHasselt

Our plea for not-building is based on the observation that not every spatial need necessarily has to lead to a new building. To architects, it is an invitation to make better use of the existing building stock, so that we must extract fewer materials and not take up unnecessary additional space. It is a healthy resistance to the mainstream building culture that we have encapsulated in our architectural practice.

We list ten tactics that can lead to space-neutral construction: intensive use of space, multiple use of space, demolition, restoration/renovation, repurposing, splitting/merging, temporary and interim use of space, reversible use of space, conscious non-use and finally tidying up. These tactics are not new in themselves, but by naming them together in an integrated strategy they can be used better and more consciously. We filter each design assignment through these ten tactics, which usually leads to alternative spatial solutions.

The ‘residual bag’ (Dutch: ‘*restzak*’) is metaphorical for our design practice: we consider thinking about what we keep and what we discard as an important design task of the architect. We have translated this design methodology into a new verb: ‘to residue’. The concept of residue addresses the question of how to deal with our existing heritage in an honourable manner at different scales. This entails dealing with existing places and buildings, as well as reducing, reusing and recycling materials, and preserving valuable mental aspects. In this context, the existing heritage can be regarded as residue.

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10 tactics to build space-neutral, *profits of not building* - RE-ST, 2015

Residual bag ('restzak') - RE-ST, 2018

Our resistance to adding unnecessarily makes us question spatial needs in every design task. British architect Cedric Price once advised a couple who sought his design expertise on a new residence that they would be better off opting for a divorce. (Wright Steenson, 2010, p. 14) Every design starts by questioning the needs. Geert Bekaert, too, argued in his essay *‘Waarom nog architecten?’* (Why Do We Still Have Architects?) that we must first gain insight into our spatial needs before translating them into built architecture.

Empirical research and concrete design issues have demonstrated that many needs can be met within the existing built space. By initially applying one or more of the ten tactics of not-building, we have successfully implemented alternative solutions on numerous occasions.

De Laatste Steen van België (Belgium's Last Stone) - Luc Deleu, 1979

Our ‘not-building’ practice was initiated in 2010 with the dual objectives of formulating a response to the financial crisis and addressing the ongoing spatial and ecological crisis. Today, we are seeing a growing awareness of the need to focus on our existing built environment in the number of invitations to lectures and debates. The challenges of the climate crisis are accelerating the focus within the architectural community on new construction methods, the need to recycle and reuse materials, and adaptive reuse.

In terms of policymaking, we are also witnessing a shift. However, we believe that the focus on the crisis at hand is often too narrow, resulting in suboptimal solutions. In terms of collective improvement of the energy performance of our building stock, combined with the EU objective of ‘No Net Land Take by 2050’, we are seeing a growing focus on reducing urban sprawl and improving the quality of our living environment. Nevertheless, we have observed instances where the replacement of existing buildings that could still serve for decades has been proposed as a means of reducing emissions. We are therefore encouraged to see initiatives such as ‘HouseEurope!’ and the extensive contemporary debate surrounding the topic of not-building with practitioners and theorists actively resisting demolition.

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Crit Journal of the American Institute of Architecture Students, 69, 14-15.

Klein Seminarie Hoogstraten

The Klein Seminarie project commenced with an open call organised by the Flemish Government Architect in 2013. In advance of selecting a designer, the school board deemed it optimal to integrate its spatial requirements with its existing historical heritage, rather than embarking on a new construction project. However, a new entrance volume and supplementary classrooms were expressly identified as necessary.

One of the key reasons the Board selected our team was our proposal to act as a steward, a metaphor for an attitude that could facilitate the progression of this process. The steward is a historical figure, analogous to a director, who is responsible for overseeing and managing existing resources. He acts in accordance with the instructions provided by his superior with the appropriate level of care. He is someone who repairs, renovates, rearranges, replaces, renews, and so on. Effective stewardship can facilitate sustainable spatial development across the entire campus. We believed that the school could potentially shrink, rather than grow, through the strategic management of available space and the relocation of certain functions. We suggested the addition of classrooms in existing, underused spaces and opposed the construction of a new entrance volume, proposing a limited intervention at the existing entrance level instead.

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Intervention at entrance area - RE-ST, picture by Stijn Bollaert, 2019

Five new classrooms were added in the historical wing - RE-ST, 2021

Due to the decline in religious observance within the school community, the protected school chapel had been largely unused in recent years. The 'mental' decay had set in, leading to faster physical decay as well. While awaiting a comprehensive restoration, we conducted one-to-one design research with the client and users to test the plural use of the chapel. Our approach was primarily practical, focusing on discovery rather than conceptualisation. Our initial proposal of using the chapel as a quiet study area evolved through collaboration with teachers and students.

Over the course of a week, the benches were temporarily removed to make way for new school activities. In the vacated chapel, various initiatives were set up and operated. These included a capoeira session, a lie-down concert, a floorboard game, and a fashion show on traffic-safe clothing. By experiencing and creating together, we demonstrated how architecture and appropriation can be put into practice. We used this instant use as a tool within the design research.

It is evident that the chapel was not a suitable candidate for adaptations or renovations. However, the space is ideal for use as a strategic asset. Its location and size make the chapel suitable for a variety of purposes and user groups. The school could utilise it as part of their study rooms, playground, classrooms and logistics. The neighbourhood could use it as a centrally located open indoor space for performances, cultural events, lectures, auditorium use and more. There are numerous potential applications, they just need to be identified.

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During a participation process with students and teachers, the chapel was used in various ways while conducting research - RE-ST, 2014

Movable altar - RE-ST, 2016

The transformation of Klein Seminarie should not be understood as an architectural task, but as an urban planning process, aiming to create a long-term urban design with architectural interventions that will meet future needs. The impact of the intensive and multiple use of the chapel over a short period of time is still being felt. Following this period, discussions were held regarding its potential use as a municipal cultural centre and a teacher was assigned the task of creating a calendar of activities. The rediscovery of the space has resulted in the creation of a versatile venue for poetry, film, media, dance, music and visual art. The original concrete altar has been replaced with a new movable altar, optimising the use of the choir area so the school could once again be opened to residents and visitors of Hoogstraten.

Diagram indicating the underused spaces of the school - RE-ST, in collaboration with baukuh, 2014

Cloister Vorselaar

The *Zusters der Christelijke Scholen van Vorselaar* (Sisters of the Christian Schools of Vorselaar) are located in the centre of Vorselaar. The Sisters founded several schools on this site, including the Cardinal Van Roey Institute (a secondary school with boarding facilities), Windekind (a primary school) and the Duizendpoot (a nursery school). The site is also home to the teacher training campus of University College Thomas More. We conducted an exploration of the spatial potential of the building block around the cloister.

Aerial view - municipality of Vorselaar, 2010

The exploration yielded a series of recommendations addressing key themes such as optimal space utilisation, reinforcement of green structures and enhanced mobility. These recommendations collectively form a strategic framework that enables the sustainable integration of future transformations within the Vorselaar context. In line with these recommendations, we were commissioned to develop a master plan for the Cardinal Van Roey Institute and a redevelopment study for the cloister buildings of the Sisters of Vorselaar.

As part of this latter study, two interventions were implemented at the cloister. The first involved furnishing a new day room for the sisters by optimising underused space within the cloister. This allowed us to persuade them to shelve their original plans for a new building in the English garden. This intervention ultimately required less than half the investment and the entire process, from initial concept to completion, took less than half a year. The second intervention related to the planned new location of the library.

During the study period, a meeting with the mayor of Vorselaar revealed that, in addition to our study, a process was underway to relocate the municipal library to a new location. We were informed that a new volume next to the monastery was being designed, with construction plans ready to be implemented. We saw an opportunity to utilise the monastery's substantial underused spatial potential. By presenting a sketch developed during the meeting, we were able to persuade the mayor to consider an alternative site.

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Repurposing study - RE-ST, 2022
Furnishing library - VOET architectuur, 2023-2024

Following the completion of our utilisation scan, we convened several meetings with the relevant parties, namely the sisters and the foundation responsible for the management of their patrimony. The objective of these meetings was to persuade them to include the municipal library in the cloister. In this instance, our role was that of mediator between the various parties, with the objective of ensuring that all parties were aligned. We reconciled the needs of the municipality and the foundation by addressing the financial aspects of the situation. From the perspective of the municipality, the investment cost in the existing, underused former reception room represented a significant saving in comparison to the construction of a new building. From the perspective of the foundation, a leasehold arrangement offered the dual benefit of additional revenue and a reduction in the number of square metres that they were required to maintain.

While the foundation and the municipality were primarily concerned with financial matters, the sisters required assurance regarding the spatial impact on their operations. Using drawings, we illustrated how we could guarantee their privacy while ensuring they had direct access to the space. This also means that the library is used by the Sisters of Vorselaar during the day, which brings the residents of Vorselaar closer to them. Following the initial planning stages, Voet Architectuur was engaged in early 2023 to develop the designs. Using a co-creation process, a new layout as a third space was devised for the library. In 2024, significantly earlier than would have been possible in a new building, the library opened its doors to the public.

In a series of workshops, the designers and the library team considered the library as a place that provides proximity. The concept of proximity was considered in two distinct ways: firstly, in terms of the library's physical accessibility as a convenient and easily accessible space, and secondly, in terms of its mental proximity as a prominent and well-known landmark within the local community. The library thus became a space that was accessible to all, offering inspiration, learning opportunities and a place to meet. A designated area for reading, a quiet study space, a coffee corner and a playful reading landscape for children all serve to promote this. The reception room has been restored to its original state. The design enhances the authentic neo-Gothic space with a glass dome and a colourful tiled floor by combining existing bookcases and new elements in green-blue and yellow. The new furnishings, including the bar and the reading tables, were created in collaboration with the technical department of Vorselaar and the students of the third-grade woodworking class at KOSH Herentals.

Designmuseum DING! Ghent

In collaboration with ATAMA (Ghent) and Carmody Groarke (London), our team was awarded the commission for the extension of the Design Museum in Ghent. The museum comprised the listed main building, Hotel de Coninck, constructed in the 18th century, the adjacent historic building, Huis Leten, and a new modern wing constructed in 1992. Since the early 1970s, the adjacent site has offered the opportunity to expand the museum with a new entrance, shop, museum café, workshop space, additional museum space and extra space for storage. A preliminary feasibility study indicated the necessity for a two-storey subterranean extension and a minimum of six to seven storeys above ground. From the outset, our design team sought to limit this new volume. Due to the water-sensitive subsoil, we opted for a single subterranean layer, and given the sensitivity of the morphology of Ghent city centre, we envisioned a maximum of five layers above ground, foregoing a tower volume.

The proposal to construct a smaller volume inevitably entailed a necessity to identify additional square meters within the preexisting museum infrastructure. This was achieved through strategic spatial optimisation, including the incorporation of the museum cafe within Huis Leten, enhanced utilisation of the existing '92 wing, and a more effective allocation of the attics.

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The new volume is located at the *Drabstraat* - Carmody Groarke, RE-ST, ATAMA, 2019
Courtyard - Carmody Groarke, RE-ST, ATAMA, 2019

Although the most recent wing was not originally included in the competition brief, this space presented a number of challenges in relation to insulation, acoustics and moisture. Furthermore, the space was unsuitable for hosting larger exhibitions. Consequently, our proposal entailed the removal of the existing voids and stairs, thereby addressing the aforementioned issues and creating an additional 600 m² of space. Between the existing wing and the new wing of DING!, we installed a new staircase, replacing the old one.

The design of the additional DING! volume was developed in a circular fashion, employing techniques such as cross-laminated timber (CLT) construction and the utilisation of a circular facade brick crafted from locally sourced construction waste, in partnership with BC Architects. However, it is the circular reuse of the existing spaces that offers the most substantial benefits.

Museum Café in *Huis Leten* - Carmody Groarke, RE-ST, ATAMA, 2019

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View from *Korenmarkt* - Carmody Groarke, RE-ST, ATAMA, 2019
Fabrication of circular brick in collaboration with BC architects - Design Museum Ghent, 2022

GO! Ensor Institute Ostend

The commission for this research was directly attributable to our BWMSTR-Label. Following a visit to our exhibition on 'Wanderspace', during which we presented examples of our utilisation scan, a design research tool that we have developed, the GO! Ensor Institute in Ostend requested that we investigate the underutilised spaces of a large-scale campus that is home to three schools.

The school board was of the opinion that there was an excess of space available and wished to ascertain whether it would be feasible to accommodate an additional school within the existing campus, with the existing facilities being adapted to meet the school's contemporary need for a more diverse range of both larger and smaller classrooms. It was necessary to ascertain whether their supposition was accurate and to identify the areas of surplus space. To this end, we commenced by examining the physical norm, defined as the global maximum gross surface area a school is entitled to in accordance with the subsidisation criteria set out by AGIO. This revealed that the campus in question had an area surplus of 40%.

Aware that there was a surplus of available space, we initiated the utilisation scan. A variety of charts were employed to facilitate the analysis and visualisation of the existing utilisation, alongside the depiction of the

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This diagram represents the underutilisation of a school and is translated into a utilisation scan. Based on this, further design research can be conducted to reduce this underutilisation.

Scan, unsolicited advice, first Master practicals, supervised by Tim Vekemans - UHasselt, 2017

underutilisation in both spatial and temporal terms. The analysis yielded insights into two areas where improvements could be made. On the one hand, a third of the classrooms were not in use at any given time of day, indicating underutilisation in terms of time. On the other hand, classrooms were often occupied by a class group of a size that was smaller than optimal, indicating underutilisation of space. Through the splitting and merging of different spaces, we demonstrated the potential for a new range of classrooms with a more efficient and intensive use of the existing space. This optimisation resulted in sufficient space being freed up to avoid the necessity for a new building for the additional school on the campus.

The process of not building typically progresses relatively rapidly. By renovating the Ensor Institute and integrating the new school, GO! was able to save a significant amount of time and generate substantial financial benefits by avoiding the costs associated with constructing a new building. It demonstrates how stakeholders can be convinced of the merits of not-building by presenting the potential financial and temporal savings that could be realised through this approach. The activation of wander space and the practice of not-building frequently result in benefits for multiple stakeholders. It is often possible to address spatial needs efficiently in the short term, and repurposing existing space is usually quickly accepted and embraced. The Go! Ensor Institute exemplifies the vast amount of underutilised space, a problem that is not only occurring within the education sector.

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Historical picture first wing - Beeldbank Oostende

The site in its wider context - RE-ST, 2021

Optimisation study - RE-ST, 2019

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These seven questions serve as a framework for our design process, informing decision-making at all stages. In addition to defining the spatial requirements, the decision of whether to retain the “residue” is also a crucial consideration. Our design research methodology encompasses utilisation scans, co-creation sessions, and experimental test phases, enabling us to gain a comprehensive grasp on present and prospective utilisation patterns. This enables us to propose optimal solutions that align with the identified needs, minimising the necessity for new construction and maximising the potential of the existing “residue.”

The potential for the detection and activation of underutilised space is considerable. There is a significant opportunity to re-examine the potential of the existing built environment. However, our experience of undertaking projects and carrying out case studies has led us to conclude that it is not simply a matter of identifying potential opportunities; rather, it is of greater importance to persuade clients to engage with these possibilities. A common thread runs through our projects: a successful one will have a client who is receptive to a dialogue about use and reuse. In this respect, the client determines the form that a narrative should take. The intended result is often similar, but the conversation can be approached from a spatial, financial, or ecological angle. The role of the mediator is to sense which approach would be most efficacious at any given time and to construct a narrative together via sketches and tables.

- Can we design with what has already been used?
- Can we avoid discarding things that are still valuable?
- Can we restore what has physically or mentally decayed?
- Can we determine the opposite of waste?
- Can we be satisfied with enough?
- Can we assume that everything is finite?
- Can we see further ahead by looking back longer?

'Can we be satisfied with enough?'

Sketch by Kristof Ribus commissioned by RE-ST for the leaflet 'residu-eren'.

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RE-ST is an architecture and research studio that searches for answers to urgent and complex spatial issues. Through projects and research processes, RE-ST searches for critical insights and visions on the built and open space that remains to us. Their position is that not every spatial need necessarily has to lead to a new building.

RE-ST is active in building and not-building, ranging from the design, repurposing and restoration of buildings, study and master planning, optimisation of the construction program, multiple programming, to the design of public spaces. The research into the benefits of not-building in 2014 was an initial search for a conscious resistance to building, and also inspiration for several design processes of current architectural projects.

In 2020, Wanderspace / Zwerf ruimte (©2020, NAi publisher) was published, in which the methodology for detecting and dealing with underutilisation of space was described in detail.

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